

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract

As a foreign language in the world, English is most often studied. Never before have you had so many educational materials, articles promising secret approaches to learning, or online communities that could support you. But if you need to learn English quickly – what is the easiest way to get a result?

In this guide, we have collected:

Techniques that have been proven to provide rapid progress.

The reasons why they work.

Some resources that can help you follow these techniques.

Key words: method, technique, material, process, result.

Traditional methods of learning a foreign language are the methods of cognition that are used in school. All the others are called unconventional. But this does not mean that they are new or unrecognized.

Their most significant difference from the generally accepted system is that non-traditional methods radically disagree with classical methods, therefore they offer their own ways of learning a foreign language.

The necessity and benefits of learning a foreign language are obvious. But how to choose a method that will help, and not slow down in this complex process?

Why are there so many of them?

Recently, on the Internet you can find a huge number of techniques for learning English quickly. There is an urgent need to evaluate them, search for advantages and disadvantages, so that people can choose the right one for themselves according to their own temperament, free time and level of training.

Let's get acquainted with the most effective and modern methods of learning English, which, if desired, it is quite possible to master yourself.

Milashevich 's method

Vladislav Milashevich is distinguished by an amazing ability to provide the most important information in the form of understandable, well-systematized material, diagrams and tables.

Here are the principles that guided the author when creating his system:

1. Systematic presentation of the material.

2. Visibility. All data is presented in the form of simple and understandable diagrams, tables and pictures that easily tell even about the most complex aspects of grammar (prepositions, tenses, etc.).

3. Compact view.

4. Focus on the speed of assimilation. This method has been specially developed for a quick way to learn any foreign language (in particular English). Thus, graduate students who were completely unfamiliar with English after several classes could understand quite difficult to assimilate material from foreign scientific journals.

5. Bold pitch. Milashevich was the creator of almost the only system that so boldly and quickly involved the student in a world unlike anything else, where it was simply told about the complex.

Leventhal 's method

This author created his methodology on the basis of a living American language, which could not be found anywhere: neither in textbooks, nor in school teachers.

And here are its basic principles:

1. Honesty. This technique does not tell you that learning will be easy and you can succeed quickly. She immediately declares that only diligence and daily hard work will lead to the desired goal.

2. Orientation to emigrants from the CIS countries. That's why the technique includes a lot of humor, slang, idioms of the USA, which will help you quickly "integrate" into local life.

Ilona Davydova's Express Method

Back in the early 90s, there was advertising everywhere about fabulously fast learning of English using this method. The deception was that the method guaranteed rapid learning of the language by the invisible and inaudible influence of certain special signals that helped English words to penetrate into our head without much effort and successfully gain a foothold there.

However, the attached books and cassettes were pretty good, so they could be used and achieve positive results.

Here are the main features of the method:

1. The material provided is not related, it looks in the form of separate voiced phrases and words. The main objective of the course is the perception of speech by ear.

2. It may be of interest to those who already have a certain knowledge base and want to increase their vocabulary.

The Schechter method and the Kitaygorodskaya communicative methodology

Learning a foreign language using the Schechter method became widespread in the distant 90s, despite the fact that they were not advertised as fiercely as learning English using the Ilona Davydova method.

The main principle of these two methods is learning through communication.

Features of the methods of Schechter and Kitaygorodskaya:

1. You do not need to learn a language, you need to create conditions that will help a person to speak a foreign language.

2. Such traditional ways of learning a foreign language as tests, exams, rules, etc. break people. Education is possible only in the absence of violence. Therefore, grammar and homework are banned here at the initial stage.

3. Live speech should not be constructed, but generated. The learning process takes place in the form of active cognitive activity, colored emotionally.

4. Everyone has the right to convey the meaning in words that correspond specifically to his life experience. The primacy of the right to freedom of choice.

5. The task of the teacher is to determine only the beginning of the event, briefly setting the direction of the climax. The denouement is impossible to predict, which is why the method is so interesting.

6. The course consists of three cycles, each of which lasts 100 hours. Between cycles, a break of 1 to 3 months should be taken, during which the student should actively read in English, watch foreign films and discuss them, listen to songs.

This is a revolutionary method for developing creativity in both students and teachers.

Zamyatkin 's method

This technique is often called "matrix", and it also has a rational grain.

1. Embedding the material into memory by repeated listening.

2. Repeated pronunciation of the listened texts, and they should be pronounced as loudly as possible.

3. Impact on the deep, unconscious structures of the brain by connecting the movements of the speech apparatus with the auditory.

Baitukalov 's method

The following principles prevail in this matrix methodology:

1. Regular classes. You should devote at least 1 hour daily to learning the language.

2. Audiobooks and videos with subtitles in a foreign language are used as the main means of learning.

3. The main way to assimilate new material is to reproduce foreign speech in a state of ignorance (mechanical memorization).

4. Understanding is not the main thing. It is important to copy foreign speech as accurately as possible.

5. It is possible to learn the meaning of what has been studied only when the material has been thoroughly worked out.

Gromyko 's method

The basic principles of this technique are as follows:

1. Memory is not used to learn English.

2. Constantly train those organs that are somehow responsible for speech (mouth, tongue, ears, eyes) by repeatedly repeating the same expressions, words.

3. You need to work only with those materials that are interesting to the student at the moment.

4. It is necessary to train not one, but at least three foreign languages. Then the learning process takes place as efficiently as possible, and the student achieves more significant results.

Dragunkin 's method

Alexander Dragunkin also came out of the shadows in the early 90s. And his system may be of interest to the following:

1. Integrity. Almost all sections of grammar are well covered in the method. the rules are clearly set out, an exercise for fixing them is presented.

2. Grammar basics are presented in an accessible way by getting acquainted with alternative grammar.

3. The rate of assimilation of the material is huge. The entire course can be mastered in 10-20 days. After that, it is proposed to carry out independent work.

4. It is fundamentally important to understand why it is important to build a phrase in this way, and not in another way.

5. Already in the first lesson, they begin to build proposals of all levels of complexity.

6. The purpose of the methodology is to lay the foundation, after which it is gradually built up (increasing the passive and active vocabulary, improving grammar, and so on).

Petrov 's method

Learning English by the method of Dmitry Petrov has its own characteristics:

1. Well-developed videos, well-honed presentation of the material.

2. Fast course completion rate. The usual program consists of 16 hours. The maximum duration of training in this way is 6 weeks.

3. Much attention is paid to watching movies for immersion in the language environment.

4. There is no need to memorize the rules, as well as complex grammatical schemes and constructions.

Pimsler 's method

Learning English by the method of Dr. Pimsler also has the right to exist, and that's why:

1. Consistency. The method is a well-designed system of 13 consecutive lessons.

2. The same importance of both listening and playing the material.

3. Each lesson should be voiced by two persons – a Russian speaker and a native speaker.

Frank 's method

Learning English by the method of Ilya Frank is based on reading literature adapted in a special way. Its features are as follows:

1. The translation of information is provided after small fragments and is framed in brackets.

2. Large sentences are divided into small fragments, separate phrases. After reading the text with "crutches" (the so-called tips in the form of translations), the same text follows, but without translation.

3. Rapid increase of passive vocabulary.

The Umin method

His method of auditory and motor engrams is described in just 50 pages. It is based on the automatic learning of English by pronouncing and perceiving phrases. And here are its features:

1. The method of engrams (the method of "memory traces") is based on the example of the peculiarities of speech assimilation in toddlers. The author also used his own knowledge about the mechanisms of the brain in the learning process.

2. Structured system of daily classes. Great success can be achieved by devoting only 15-20 minutes to training every day.

3. The ability to reach a level equal to a native speaker, proportionally increasing the time of daily study.

Rosetta Stone has dedicated her methodology to those who spend a lot of time at the computer. But this is not all of its features:

1. Gradual immersion of the user into the language environment of the native speaker.

2. No quick transitions from simple to complex – only uniform immersion and complication.

3. Initial familiarity with simple words, smoothly transitioning to complex speech structures, syntax and grammar.

The best way to learn English

We have got acquainted with the most popular ways and methods of self-study of English from scratch. At the same time, it is necessary to understand that there is no better method of learning a foreign language among them.

With a huge number of advantages of all these methods, each of them has one big drawback: none of them guarantees an absolute, fast and effective way of learning a foreign language independently for everyone. Why?

The fact is that all people have different dominant ways of perceiving information. Some of us are auditory, that is, they perceive information mainly with the help of auditory channels. Other visuals are people who perceive and process information primarily through the visual channel. There are also kinesthetics and digitals, which also have their own characteristics.

So, each method of learning English will be effective only for one or two types of people.

Do not forget that these methods of rapid learning of the English language are focused, as a rule, not on everything, but only on some aspects of the language (grammar, vocabulary, colloquial speech, listening comprehension).

The best methods of foreign languages should be developed in such a way that each language aspect develops equally well. And such a method a priori cannot be quick and easy. In this case, it would be better to look for a good English tutor.

Therefore, we can only wait for the emergence of new unique and effective methods of self-study of foreign languages (especially English as a world language). Well, while you are waiting, there will always be a reliable friend next to you – a student help service, whose specialists will always help with translations, tests or other works in English.

As you may have guessed, the only way that really works for learning English quickly is through long practice. Remember: everyone who understands something was a beginner for a very long time at first! We are big fans of the idea that you need to learn to love your mistakes and accept them in the learning process.

How to make it easy? Incorporate English into your daily life and find ways to enjoy the process. Changing your phone settings to English, subscribing to

excellent YouTube channels about ESL and singing along to the Beatles won't be as "difficult" as working with a foreign language textbook, but all these are effective ways to master everyday English skills.

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